

Embase.com (1971-)	2655	2637
Medline ALL Ovid (1946-)	588	123
Web of science Core Collection (1975-)	404	96
Cochrane CENTRAL register of trials (1992-)	141	83
Totaal	3788	2939

Embase.com (1971-) 2655

('radiation injury'/de OR 'radiation cataract'/exp OR 'radiation dermatitis'/exp OR 'radiation induced nausea and vomiting'/exp OR 'radiation necrosis'/exp OR 'radiation nephropathy'/exp OR 'radiation pneumonia'/exp OR 'radiation sickness'/exp OR 'radiation response'/de OR (('radiotherapy'/exp OR neoplasm/exp/dm_rt) AND ('side effect'/de OR 'side effect':lnk OR 'complication'/de OR 'complication':lnk OR 'adverse event'/de) AND ('cataract'/exp OR 'dermatitis'/exp OR 'nausea and vomiting'/exp OR 'kidney disease'/de OR pneumonia/exp OR 'inflammation'/exp OR 'necrosis'/exp OR 'xerostomia'/exp OR 'swallowing'/exp OR 'dysphagia'/exp OR 'hearing disorder'/exp OR 'hypothyroidism'/exp OR 'thyroid disease'/de OR 'tinnitus'/de OR 'trismus'/de OR 'malnutrition'/exp OR 'bleeding'/de OR 'digestive system hemorrhage'/exp OR Ulcer/exp OR 'fistula'/de OR 'digestive system fistula'/exp OR 'obstruction'/de OR 'urinary tract obstruction'/exp OR 'fatigue'/exp OR 'heart arrhythmia'/exp OR 'heart disease'/exp OR 'myocardial disease'/exp OR 'cognition'/exp OR 'cognitive defect'/de OR 'toxicity'/exp)) OR (((radiation* OR irradiation* OR postradiation* OR chemoradiation* OR radiotherap* OR radioactiv* OR ion-therap* OR particle-therap* OR sbrt) NEAR/6 (injur* OR impair* OR cataract OR dermatitis OR nausea OR vomiting OR necrosis OR nephropath* OR pneumoni* OR sickness OR Mucositis OR Osteoradionecrosis OR Xerostomia OR Deglutit* OR Hearing-Loss* OR Hypothyroid* OR thyroid* OR Tinnitus OR Trismus OR Cachexia OR malnutrit* OR undernutrit* OR malabsorption* OR Hemorrhage* OR bleeding OR Ulcer* OR Fistula* OR nephritis OR Hematuria OR urinary-tract* OR Obstruct* OR Fatigue OR Pericarditis OR carditis OR Myocarditis OR Arrhythmia* OR Cardiomyopath* OR Cogniti* OR adverse* OR side-effect OR complication* OR toxic* OR ototoxic* OR morbidit* OR neuropath* OR sequel* OR cardiotoxic* OR pain* OR swallow* OR necrosis*)) OR radiodermatitis* OR radiotoxic*):ab,ti) AND ('head and neck tumor'/exp OR 'prostate tumor'/exp OR 'breast tumor'/exp OR 'brain tumor'/exp OR 'eye tumor'/exp OR (((head OR neck OR breast OR prostat* OR brain OR eye OR orbit* OR nasopharyn* OR pharyn* OR hypopharyn* OR esopharyn* OR oropharyng* OR oesopharyng* OR tongue OR oral OR mouth OR thyroid* OR face OR facial OR lip OR jaw OR mandib* OR maxilla* OR lip OR nose OR paranasal* OR tonsil* OR saliva*-gland*) NEAR/3 (cancer* OR neoplas* OR tumo* OR carcinoma* OR adenocarcinoma* OR radiotherap* OR chemoradiotherap* OR radiochemotherap* OR irradiation* OR brachytherapy* OR Metasta* OR melanom* OR rhabdomyosarcoma* OR sarcoma*)) OR glioma* OR glioblastoma* OR medulloblastoma*):ab,ti) AND ('health care utilization'/exp OR 'hospitalization'/exp OR 'medical leave'/exp OR 'absenteeism'/exp OR 'presenteeism'/exp OR 'productivity'/exp OR 'retirement'/de OR 'workforce'/de OR 'cost'/exp OR 'economic evaluation'/exp OR 'economic aspect'/exp OR 'informal care'/de OR (((health-care OR healthcare OR resource*) NEAR/3 (utilizat* OR utilisat* OR use)) OR hospitalizat* OR hospitalisat* OR ((medical OR sick) NEXT/1 (leave)) OR absenteeism* OR presenteeism* OR productivit* OR retirement* OR workforce* OR work-force* OR cost OR costs OR (economic* NEAR/3 evaluat*) OR (informal NEAR/3 (care OR carer* OR

caregiver*)):ab,ti) NOT ('case report'/de OR (case-report*):ti) NOT ([Conference Abstract]/lim) NOT ((animal/exp OR animal*:de OR nonhuman/de) NOT ('human'/exp)) AND [English]/lim

Medline ALL Ovid (1946-) 588

(Radiation Injuries/ OR Radiodermatitis/ OR Radiation Pneumonitis/ OR ((Radiotherapy/ OR exp Neoplasms/rt) AND (side effect/ OR side effect.fx. OR complication/ OR complication.fx. OR adverse event/) AND (Cataract/ OR Dermatitis/ OR nausea/ OR vomiting/ OR Kidney Diseases/ OR Pneumonia/ OR Inflammation/ OR Necrosis/ OR Xerostomia/ OR Deglutition/ OR Deglutition Disorders/ OR Hearing Disorders/ OR Hypothyroidism/ OR Thyroid Diseases/ OR Tinnitus/ OR Trismus/ OR Malnutrition/ OR Hemorrhage/ OR Gastrointestinal Hemorrhage/ OR Ulcer/ OR Fistula/ OR Digestive System Fistula/ OR obstruction/ OR urinary tract obstruction/ OR Fatigue/ OR Arrhythmias, Cardiac/ OR Heart Diseases/ OR Cardiomyopathies/ OR Cognition/ OR cognitive defect/ OR toxicity/)) OR (((radiation* OR irradiation* OR postradiation* OR chemoradiation* OR radiotherap* OR radioactiv* OR ion-therap* OR particle-therap* OR sbrt) ADJ6 (injur* OR impair* OR cataract OR dermatitis OR nausea OR vomiting OR necrosis OR nephropath* OR pneumoni* OR sickness OR Mucositis OR Osteoradionecrosis OR Xerostomia OR Deglutit* OR Hearing-Loss* OR Hypothyroid* OR thyroid* OR Tinnitus OR Trismus OR Cachexia OR malnutrit* OR undernutrit* OR malabsorption* OR Hemorrhage* OR bleeding OR Ulcer* OR Fistula* OR nephritis OR Hematuria OR urinary-tract* OR Obstruct* OR Fatigue OR Pericarditis OR carditis OR Myocarditis OR Arrhythmia* OR Cardiomyopath* OR Cogniti* OR adverse* OR side-effect OR complication* OR toxic* OR ototoxic* OR morbidit* OR neuropath* OR sequel* OR cardiotoxic* OR pain* OR swallow* OR necrosis*)) OR radiodermatitis* OR radiotoxic*).ab,ti.) AND (exp " Head and Neck Neoplasms "/ OR exp Prostatic Neoplasms/ OR exp Breast Neoplasms/ OR exp Brain Neoplasms/ OR exp Eye Neoplasms/ OR (((head OR neck OR breast OR prostat* OR brain OR eye OR orbit* OR nasopharyn* OR pharyn* OR hypopharyn* OR esopharyn* OR oropharyng* OR oesopharyng* OR tongue OR oral OR mouth OR thyroid* OR face OR facial OR lip OR jaw OR mandib* OR maxilla* OR lip OR nose OR paranasal* OR tonsil* OR saliva*-gland*) ADJ3 (cancer* OR neoplas* OR tumo* OR carcinoma* OR adenocarcinoma* OR radiotherap* OR chemoradiotherap* OR radiochemotherap* OR irradiation* OR brachytherapy* OR Metasta* OR melanom* OR rhabdomyosarcoma* OR sarcoma*)) OR glioma* OR glioblastoma* OR medulloblastoma*).ab,ti.) AND (Patient Acceptance of Health Care/ OR Hospitalization/ OR Sick Leave/ OR Absenteeism/ OR Presenteeism/ OR Efficiency/ OR Retirement/ OR Workforce/ OR "Costs and Cost Analysis"/ OR Cost-Benefit Analysis/ OR Economics/ OR (((health-care OR healthcare OR resource*) ADJ3 (utilizat* OR utilisat* OR "use")) OR hospitalizat* OR hospitalisat* OR ((medical OR sick) ADJ (leave)) OR absenteeism* OR presenteeism* OR productivit* OR retirement* OR workforce* OR work-force* OR cost OR costs OR (economic* ADJ3 evaluat*) OR (informal ADJ3 (care OR carer* OR caregiver*))).ab,ti.) NOT (case report/ OR (case-report*).ti.) NOT (news OR congres* OR abstract* OR book* OR chapter* OR dissertation abstract*).pt. NOT ((exp animal/) NOT (human/)) AND english.la.

Web of science Core Collection (1975-) 404

TS=(((radiation* OR irradiation* OR postradiation* OR chemoradiation* OR radiotherap* OR radioactiv* OR ion-therap* OR particle-therap* OR sbrt) NEAR/5 (injur* OR impair* OR cataract OR dermatitis OR nausea OR vomiting OR necrosis OR nephropath* OR pneumoni* OR sickness OR Mucositis OR Osteoradionecrosis OR Xerostomia OR Deglutit* OR Hearing-Loss* OR Hypothyroid* OR thyroid* OR Tinnitus OR Trismus OR Cachexia OR malnutrit* OR undernutrit* OR malabsorption* OR

Hemorrhage* OR bleeding OR Ulcer* OR Fistula* OR nephritis OR Hematuria OR urinary-tract* OR Obstruct* OR Fatigue OR Pericarditis OR carditis OR Myocarditis OR Arrhythmia* OR Cardiomyopath* OR Cogniti* OR adverse* OR side-effect OR complication* OR toxic* OR ototoxic* OR morbidit* OR neuropath* OR sequel* OR cardiotoxic* OR pain* OR swallow* OR necrosis*) OR radiodermatitis* OR radiotoxic*) AND (((head OR neck OR breast OR prostat* OR brain OR eye OR orbit* OR nasopharyn* OR pharyn* OR hypopharyn* OR esopharyn* OR oropharyng* OR oesopharyng* OR tongue OR oral OR mouth OR thyroid* OR face OR facial OR lip OR jaw OR mandib* OR maxilla* OR lip OR nose OR paranasal* OR tonsil* OR saliva*-gland*) NEAR/2 (cancer* OR neoplas* OR tumo* OR carcinoma* OR adenocarcinoma* OR radiotherap* OR chemoradiotherap* OR radiochemotherap* OR irradiation* OR brachytherapy* OR Metasta* OR melanom* OR rhabdomyosarcoma* OR sarcoma*)) OR glioma* OR glioblastoma* OR medulloblastoma*)) AND (((health-care OR healthcare OR resource*) NEAR/2 (utilizat* OR utilisat* OR use)) OR hospitalizat* OR hospitalisat* OR ((medical OR sick) NEAR/1 (leave)) OR absenteeism* OR presenteeism* OR productivit* OR retirement* OR workforce* OR work-force* OR cost OR costs OR (economic* NEAR/2 evaluat*) OR (informal NEAR/2 (care OR carer* OR caregiver*)))) NOT TI=("case stud*" OR "case report*") AND DT=(article) AND LA=(english)

Cochrane CENTRAL register of trials (1992-) 141

((((radiation* OR irradiation* OR postradiation* OR chemoradiation* OR radiotherap* OR radioactiv* OR ion-therap* OR particle-therap* OR sbrt) NEAR/6 (injur* OR impair* OR cataract OR dermatitis OR nausea OR vomiting OR necrosis OR nephropath* OR pneumoni* OR sickness OR Mucositis OR Osteoradionecrosis OR Xerostomia OR Deglutit* OR Hearing-Loss* OR Hypothyroid* OR thyroid* OR Tinnitus OR Trismus OR Cachexia OR malnutrit* OR undernutrit* OR malabsorption* OR Hemorrhage* OR bleeding OR Ulcer* OR Fistula* OR nephritis OR Hematuria OR urinary-tract* OR Obstruct* OR Fatigue OR Pericarditis OR carditis OR Myocarditis OR Arrhythmia* OR Cardiomyopath* OR Cogniti* OR adverse* OR side-effect OR complication* OR toxic* OR ototoxic* OR morbidit* OR neuropath* OR sequel* OR cardiotoxic* OR pain* OR swallow* OR necrosis*)) OR radiodermatitis* OR radiotoxic*):ab,ti) AND (((head OR neck OR breast OR prostat* OR brain OR eye OR orbit* OR nasopharyn* OR pharyn* OR hypopharyn* OR esopharyn* OR oropharyng* OR oesopharyng* OR tongue OR oral OR mouth OR thyroid* OR face OR facial OR lip OR jaw OR mandib* OR maxilla* OR lip OR nose OR paranasal* OR tonsil* OR saliva* NEXT gland*) NEAR/3 (cancer* OR neoplas* OR tumo* OR carcinoma* OR adenocarcinoma* OR radiotherap* OR chemoradiotherap* OR radiochemotherap* OR irradiation* OR brachytherapy* OR Metasta* OR melanom* OR rhabdomyosarcoma* OR sarcoma*)) OR glioma* OR glioblastoma* OR medulloblastoma*):ab,ti) AND (((health-care OR healthcare OR resource*) NEAR/3 (utilizat* OR utilisat* OR use)) OR hospitalizat* OR hospitalisat* OR ((medical OR sick) NEXT/1 (leave)) OR absenteeism* OR presenteeism* OR productivit* OR retirement* OR workforce* OR work-force* OR cost OR costs OR (economic* NEAR/3 evaluat*) OR (informal NEAR/3 (care OR carer* OR caregiver*)))):ab,ti)

